

THERMOPLASTIC HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPOSITES: ENVIRONMENTAL REQUIREMENTS ON FUTURE HELICOPTER AIRFRAMES

P.P. Parlevliet, C. Weimer*

Laboratories for Materials & Processes

Eurocopter Deutschland GmbH, 81663 Munich, Germany

* Corresponding author (christian.weimer@eurocopter.com)

1 Introduction

Future helicopter (HC) airframe structures are aimed to provide higher value to the customers or end-users. This increased value can be created by increased payload, enlarged mission capabilities (range, flight envelope, speed, ...), optimised long-life solutions, improved availability, economical operation, environmental impact and other factors (passenger comfort, noise, ...). These 'Helicopter customer values' can be offered by adopting improved materials and processes and thus new manufacturing technologies, such as High Performance Thermoplastic Composites (HPTC) [1]. However, production cost is a key element for the manufacturer to access and exploit a new technology like HPTCs, even if the technical benefits are given. Therefore, this paper aims to identify the specific requirements and challenges for future helicopter airframe structures and to discuss the related potential of HPTC. A main focus is placed on customer value and sustainability.

In addition, current hurdles to enlarge the use of HPTC in Helicopter Airframes are addressed and explained in order to direct further basic research in this area.

2 Customer Value of Advanced Airframes

HPTC can contribute to an increased customer value due some specific advantages, which will be detailed below.

For example, an increased payload can be achieved by reduced weight of structures. In this case especially the damage tolerance of HPTC shall be mentioned, which can be considered to give structures a higher residual – after impact – performance, which is very often the defining factor during sizing of a structure.

Further weight reductions can be achieved by optimised assembly technologies, since structures can be joined by welding, which thus can prevent adhesive bonding or shimming processes. Reduced

riveting efforts in complex loaded parts can be a long-term weight-reducing result.

Enlarged mission capabilities arise from weight saving but also from design freedom and other factors like optimised abrasion behaviour or optimised performance at elevated (above 150° C) or very low temperatures (lower than –50° C). Abrasion performance often requires special surface treatments and preparation. Here solutions preventing this necessity would help to reduce efforts and weight as a consequence. High speed configurations of advanced HCs push this limits further.

In terms of long-life structures the first and dominating aim is again high damage tolerance in order to lengthen the first life of a structure. Second is the fast and secure replace- or repair- ability without loss of performance. Accessibility of the structure has to be considered, e.g. fast dismantling and reinstallation of equipments before and after repair. Non destructive inspection has to be considered at all times – during operation and after replacement or repair. Even second life usage of structures as spares can be a way of increased customer benefit.

Improving the availability of HC can be achieved by high damage tolerant structures and fast and easy repair or easy replacement solutions.

Economical operation can be achieved by many factors, some of them already being described. Most import is weight saving, going along with long-life solutions. However, the acquisition cost is another important factor, where the production technology and the productivity of the manufacture can make the difference. Also a key factor is the fast availability and the cost of spare parts.

The major environmental impact of a HC is defined by the use during life and thus, weight again plays the key role. In terms of life cycle impact, the production technology and the end-of-life solutions have to be considered as well. Here energy consumption and environmental footprint (CO₂

Emissions, Water pollution, hazardous ingredients, etc.) have to be considered as a key element.

In the future, end-of-life solutions including recycling and disassembling technologies will be more and more requested by the operating customer, who needs to cope with ISO 14000 requirements, which are driven by an environmental responsibility. However, ISO 14000 not only requires the development of the life-cycle performance of the product during manufacturing, but also life span and end-of-life. Here, HPTC can contribute significantly, since thermoplastic composites offers more options for the recycling operations, including dismantling and debonding of laminated materials.

3 Environmental Requirements

3.1 Background

Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) dedicate themselves more and more towards the entire life cycle of their products with, for example, the environmental management system ISO14001 and fulfillment of REACH or other regulations (ACARE). In Fig. 1, a general overview of a product's life cycle, including the raw materials and manufacturing processes to form a product, and its service life and end-of-life is presented. How this circle applies to helicopter airframe structures and resulting requirements is explained in the following sections.

Fig. 1. Product's life cycle.

3.2 Materials & Processes

Regarding new materials and process development it is mandatory that REACH compliance is ensured, meaning full knowledge of the use of any potentially hazardous materials and their sources., but preferably prevent use of these materials at all, looking for alternatives, to prevent future obsolescence. Furthermore, life cycle aspects and other regulative targets (ACARE) have to be considered. Here, a major point of concern is the amount of energy required to fabricate (aerospace-grade) carbon fibres and the parts themselves. Therefore, it may be of interest to look into the use of recycled carbon fibres from, for example, outdated prepregs waste. However, re-use of composite structures as well as the used materials shall be considered first, before the recycling on material level. The efforts always have to balance overall cost, weight and environmental impact, which can be analysed by LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) procedures.

During the selection of a life-cycle-appropriate material, also the processing of the semi-finished materials has to be considered and assessed taking into account the number of consolidation steps. Polymer grinding or solving as well as foil or yarn manufacturing has to be considered and evaluated regarding the impact on the environmental impact in the overall process chain.

For helicopter structural applications the following matrices for high performance thermoplastic composites (HPTC) are being considered following their special characteristics:

Polyetheretherketone: PEEK

- High viscosity
- High processing temperature (390°C)
- Excellent mechanical and thermal properties
- Excellent wear/ abrasion resistance

Polyetherketoneketone: PEKK

- Cost advantage compared to PEEK
- Good processing properties
- Disadvantage: single source availability

Polyphenylenesulfide: PPS

- Commonly used in composites for aircraft structures
- Excellent chemical resistance
- Relatively brittle

- Maximum continuous use temperature: ~100°C

Polyetherimide: PEI

- For secondary aircraft structures
- Good weldability
- Lower chemical resistance

Other polymers of interest are PES, PPSU, PSU due to their intrinsic flame retardation, and availability.

3.3 Manufacturing and Production

The most notable environmental manufacturing requirements are related to resource consumption, e.g. water and energy. In addition, new technologies should present no health, safety and other environmental (HSE) hazards. Therefore, most new manufacturing technology developments for composites are aimed in the directions of automated processes combined with Out-of-Autoclave (OoA) curing or consolidation. Examples include Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM), Vacuum-Bag-Only (VBO) curing by means of an oven, heated tooling, Quickstep® technology, as well as novel technologies for thermoplastic composites, such as OoA consolidation of customised blanks and joining by welding. Here, the aim is to *reduce cycle times* as well as *resource consumption*, while increasing the degree of *automation*, against an *affordable price*.

For HPTC automated forming and lay-up technologies are being considered for parts manufacturing. To assess the environmental footprint of these production technologies the complete process chain from raw material to the final part has to be considered. One aim of development should be a reduced number of thermal cycles exceeding the melting temperatures of the HPTC in order to keep the energy consumption as low as possible.

3.4 Long-life structures

The largest contribution to a helicopters' structure ecological footprint comes from the weight and the amount of energy required to keep it flying. Therefore, lightweight design is of paramount importance. One of Eurocopter's current focuses is on finding lightweight composite solutions for the structures including usage in elevated temperatures (service temperature up to 230°C) prone areas.

For all new materials and manufacturing technologies, the resulting structure must be durable and easy to repair. HPTC can deliver solutions for this particular requirement, however, for extreme light-weight design, appropriate unidirectional reinforced, very thin organic sheets are needed and their tailoring technologies have to be developed. Sandwich structures, which are a key for light-weight design for light- to medium-heavy helicopters, have to be available and repairable without penalty in weight compared to standard materials and processes.

3.5 End-of-life

End-of-life deals with the treatment of parts and structures after its first life. After that a dismantling and recycling operation starts, where different approaches can be followed [3]. Since the HPTC are cost intensive materials and show very good fatigue and long-term behavior, the structure and the material can outdate the life of the Helicopter as such. Thus, disassembling and re-use technologies shall be of major interest. Easy dismantling of HPTCs provides major benefits for long-life and end-of-life solutions, where damaged parts can be simply replaced, prolonging the parts and the Helicopter lifetime. Parts that still function, can be considered for a second life in another helicopter structure.

In particular for HPTC, the considered recycling technologies must be divided into recycling technologies for the material itself (carbon fibre and thermoplastic matrices) and the composite structure. In addition, the number of different materials should be kept to a minimum, enabling easier recycling and lower costs [4], when it comes to a recycling of material level. Here, paints and surface coatings have to be considered as well as contaminations inside the structure occurring during production and service of a Helicopter.

4 Case Study – Helicopter Pilot door

A helicopter pilot door (Fig. 2) is assessed as a case study for overall value creation and LCA beneficial HC airframe structures by the use of HPTCs. By using high performance thermoplastic based composites using automated rapid OoA processing and presenting a better end-of-life solution by using

recyclable materials, the aim is to present a solution with an improved ecological footprint, with equal or better performance (weight) and cost. The major technological developments include forming and final consolidation of customised blanks (composite lay-ups with dedicated fibre directions) into subcomponents. The thermoplastic composite solution provides easy dismantling and repair, using an increased temperature to melt the matrix, contributing significantly to a positive LCA.

Fig. 2: Example Helicopter Pilot Door in Composite Materials

For achieving the required environmental targets on top of the fulfillment of the increased customer value of a future helicopter airframe, in particular the integration and assembly technology is being developed. This technology shall also provide disassembly capability as well as repair opportunities.

Induction welding of HPTC is one technology being considered, in particular for its ability to provide a structural bonding quality and to be a flexible heating technology. Induction has proven to be applicable for woven fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites in the past and in several studies. However, it has to be proven, that the technology can also work with built-in lightning strike protective layers.

A further step of development in order to achieve weight optimised structures is the introduction of unidirectional reinforced tapes into the laminate in order to tailor the structure.

5 Conclusions and recommendations

This paper identifies future industrial and technological needs in the development and understanding of new composite materials and processes and in particular high performance thermoplastic composites in order to secure applicability in Helicopter structures in the future. The most important aspects for future composite helicopter airframe structures are related to the life cycle and overall environmental aspects as well as value creation for the customer by the supply of advanced airframes.

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7 References

- [1] Cetex - Thermoplastic Composites, "From Scratch to Flight", Ed. H.E.N. Bersee, G.F. Niño, Delft, Netherlands, ISBN 9789090211893, June 2006
- [2] C. Luttrup, J. Lagerstedt "EcoDesign and the Ten Golden Rules: generic advice for merging environmental aspects into product development". *J. of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 14, No. 15-16, pp 1396-1408, 2006.
- [3] <http://www.pamelalife.com>. The PAMELA (Process for Advanced Management of End of Life of Aircraft). Web page of the EU project.
- [4] P.Parlevliet, C. Weimer, Automated Joining Processes for High-Performance Thermoplastic Composite Structures, *SAMPE 2011, Long Beach CA, 23-26 May 2011*